

STRATEGIC OUTSOURCING AND PERFORMANCE OF PHARMACEUTICAL FIRMS IN ENUGU STATE

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DOI:<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15641610>

Abstract: The study evaluated strategic outsourcing and performance of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State. The specific objectives of the study are to; examine the relationship between technological advancements and operational efficiency; and evaluate the relationship between payment selection and reduced costs of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State. The area of the study comprised of four (4) selected Pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in Enugu metropolis. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. A total population of 253 selected staff of the study organizations. The study made use of the whole population due to small size. Two hundred and twenty four (224) staff returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. Data was presented and analyzed by mean score and standard deviation using Sprint Likert Scale. The hypotheses were analyzed using Z – test statistic tool. The findings indicated that Technological advancements had significant positive relationship with operational efficiency $Z(9.235, P. <.05)$ and Payment selection had significant positive relationship with reduced costs of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State $Z(10.755, P. <.05)$. The study concluded that Technological advancements and Payment selection had significant positive relationship with operational efficiency and reduced costs of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State. The study recommended among others that Pharmaceutical firms should adopt advanced manufacturing systems such as Continuous Manufacturing (CM) and Process Analytical Technology (PAT). These technologies allow for, Real-time monitoring and control of production processes, and reduced downtime and waste, and faster product throughput and improved quality assurance.

Keywords: Strategic outsourcing, technological advancements, operational efficiency, payment selection, reduced costs & performance.

Introduction

1.1 Background of the Study

With the evolution of businesses, many companies are turning to strategic outsourcing to improve their performance, reduce workload, and focus on their main business activities. Strategic outsourcing means hiring

outside experts or companies to handle some of the work that a business would normally do in-house. It is not just about saving money but also about improving the way a business works, encouraging innovation, and increasing competitiveness (Lacity and Willcocks, 2017). In the pharmaceutical industry, especially in developing countries like Nigeria, outsourcing is becoming more important due to high production costs, poor infrastructure, and strict regulations. Companies in this sector face many challenges and need new ways to operate more effectively and stay in business (Okeke and Onuoha, 2020; Ezenwakwelu and Onwurah, 2021).

One major area where outsourcing has helped is in the use of modern technology. Digital tools like cloud computing, online inventory management, and data-sharing platforms have made it easier for businesses to manage outsourced activities. These tools help improve efficiency, communication, and speed of service (Arlbjørn and Lüthje, 2017). For pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State, where access to modern facilities may be limited, outsourcing with the help of technology can improve operations and service delivery (Okoro and Nwankwo, 2019). Also, companies can focus more on key areas like research and medicine development when they outsource tasks like IT services, transportation, or marketing. Another important aspect of outsourcing is payment. Using flexible and digital payment methods can reduce the cost of doing business, make financial transactions faster, and reduce errors (Chikwe and Onoh, 2021).

In Nigeria, the pharmaceutical sector is under pressure to meet increasing health needs with limited resources. Strategic outsourcing offers a way for firms in Enugu State to handle these problems by improving efficiency and saving costs. Previous studies have shown that when companies use outsourcing properly and support it with good technology and payment systems, they perform better (Akinbami and Bello, 2020; Edeh and Ugochukwu, 2021). However, results may differ based on how outsourcing is planned and managed. This study will look at how two parts of outsourcing, which are technology and payment selection, affect the performance of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State. It will focus on whether these factors lead to better operations and lower costs. The study hopes to help business leaders, researchers, and policy makers understand how outsourcing can improve the way pharmaceutical firms operate in this part of Nigeria.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

In an ideal business environment, pharmaceutical firms would operate with high efficiency, minimal costs, and the ability to quickly respond to customer and market demands. Strategic outsourcing would serve as a key tool for achieving these goals. Through outsourcing, firms can delegate non-core tasks such as logistics, IT services, and payroll processing to specialized providers, allowing them to focus on their core mission of drug research, production, and marketing. When supported by modern technology and flexible payment systems, outsourcing can enhance performance, boost operational speed, and reduce the burden on internal resources. In such a situation, pharmaceutical firms would consistently maintain high standards of service, remain competitive, and contribute meaningfully to public health and economic development.

However, this ideal is not the reality for many pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State. Despite the growing awareness of outsourcing as a strategic business practice, many firms either underutilize it or fail to apply it effectively. The lack of technological innovation and poor payment structures has made it difficult for these firms to fully enjoy the benefits of outsourcing. As a result, tasks that could be outsourced remain inefficiently

handled in-house, leading to slow service delivery, poor inventory management, and rising operational costs. These challenges directly relate to the specific objectives of this study, which aim to examine the relationship between technological advancement and operational efficiency, and between payment selection and reduced costs. Without proper outsourcing frameworks, firms struggle to meet demand, maintain quality standards, and adapt to market changes.

The consequence of ignoring or mismanaging strategic outsourcing is a continuous decline in the performance and competitiveness of pharmaceutical firms. High operational costs, duplication of effort, and weak service delivery result in loss of customers, reduced profit margins, and inability to scale operations. This poor performance may also lead to job losses and limited access to quality healthcare products in the region. In the long term, the entire health system may suffer if these firms are unable to meet growing health needs or respond effectively during public health emergencies. Thus, the failure to apply strategic outsourcing with the right technology and payment systems not only affects firm performance but also poses a broader risk to economic growth and public welfare in Enugu State.

1.3 Research Objectives

The broad objective of the study is to evaluate strategic outsourcing and performance of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State. The specific objectives of the study are to;

- i. Examine the relationship between technological advancements and operational efficiency of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State.
- ii. Evaluate the relationship between payment selection and reduced costs of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State.

1.4 Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

- i. What is the relationship between technological advancements and operational efficiency of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State?
- ii. What is the relationship between payment selection and reduced costs of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State?

1.5 Statement of Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses guided the study;

- i. Technological advancements have no positive relationship with operational efficiency of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State.
- ii. Payment selection has no positive relationship with reduced costs of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State.

1.6 Significance of the Study

This study is significant because it explores how strategic outsourcing, particularly through technological advancements and payment systems, affects the performance of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State. In an era where firms face growing operational demands, rising costs, and intense competition, outsourcing non-core activities has become a critical strategy for survival and growth. By examining the impact of technology on

operational efficiency, the study will offer insights into how digital tools can help pharmaceutical firms streamline their processes and deliver services more effectively. Moreover, the study investigates how payment selection strategies can reduce transaction and operational costs. These findings will be useful to pharmaceutical business owners, managers, and stakeholders in making informed decisions about outsourcing. The study also contributes to academic literature by filling a gap in the context-specific understanding of outsourcing in Nigeria's pharmaceutical sector. Policymakers and industry regulators may also benefit from the research, as it could guide the development of support systems that enhance efficiency and cost management among health-related enterprises.

1.7 Scope of the Study

The scope of this study is limited to pharmaceutical firms operating in Enugu State, Nigeria. It focuses on two key aspects of strategic outsourcing: technological advancements and payment selection. The study will investigate how these variables relate to the operational efficiency and cost reduction of the selected firms. Geographically, the study is restricted to Enugu State, which was chosen due to its growing pharmaceutical sector and strategic role as a commercial hub in southeastern Nigeria. The study targets managers, supervisors, and key operational staff who are directly involved in outsourcing decisions and daily operations. It will not cover other sectors or outsourcing types beyond technology and payment systems. The time frame of analysis is current and recent enough to reflect present challenges and trends within the industry. The study will use a quantitative research approach, gathering data through structured questionnaires to ensure objectivity and reliability of findings.

Review of Related Literature

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Strategic Outsourcing

Outsourcing can be defined as the process which a company contract non-core process with another company to provide services that might otherwise be performed by within employees (Sako, 2016). Egole & Iheriohanma (2020) defined outsourcing is an arrangement by which one firm provides services to another firm that could be done within or is the transfer of some operations or functions to external service providers that, such authority is delegated to another party for the provision of services under a business contract that incorporates service level agreements related to cost, quality and timely delivery of product and service. Outsourcing enables firms to tap into new ideas, knowledge and creativity through access to service providers' resources like skills, experience, specialized equipment and investments to provide services of better quality, at lower costs than in-house departments (Okoye, 2021). Strategic outsourcing is the practice where a company deliberately hires another firm to handle certain business functions, especially those that are not central to its main operations. This helps the company focus on its core strengths while still getting high-quality services for tasks like IT, customer service, logistics, or accounting. Kayumba (2019) also defined outsourcing known as a good technique for management can be defined as the strategy of using outside resources to implement activities traditionally managed by internal staff.

2.1.1.1 Technological Advancements

Technological advancements have significantly transformed the global economic and financial landscape. In the financial sector, innovations such as mobile banking, internet banking, blockchain, artificial intelligence, and cloud computing have redefined how individuals and businesses conduct financial transactions. These technologies have enabled faster, more secure, and more convenient service delivery while also reducing operational costs for service providers. For instance, blockchain technology enhances transparency and security in transactions through decentralized ledger systems, thus reducing fraud (Tapscott & Tapscott, 2016). Similarly, artificial intelligence and machine learning are used to analyze consumer behavior, detect fraud, and personalize financial services, thereby improving customer experience (Arner, Barberis, & Buckley, 2016). In Nigeria and across Africa, mobile technologies have bridged gaps in financial inclusion, enabling millions to access financial services through platforms such as M-Pesa and Opay (Ozili, 2018). The continuous evolution of technology not only supports more efficient financial systems but also facilitates economic growth by promoting innovation and accessibility.

2.1.1.2 Payment Selection

Payment selection refers to the variety of methods individuals and organizations use to settle transactions, influenced by preferences, access to technology, security, and cost. Over the years, payment systems have evolved from cash-based methods to digital and contactless options including debit/credit cards, online transfers, mobile wallets, and cryptocurrencies. The increased availability of digital payment channels has enhanced convenience, reduced transaction times, and promoted transparency in financial dealings (Zhou, Lu, & Wang, 2010). In Nigeria, the Central Bank has encouraged the adoption of electronic payment systems through policies like the cashless policy, which aims to reduce the dominance of cash in the economy and improve the efficiency of payments (CBN, 2019). The COVID-19 pandemic further accelerated the shift towards contactless and digital payments as consumer's prioritized safety and hygiene (Auer, Cornelli, & Frost, 2020). However, factors such as internet penetration, digital literacy, and trust in technology still influence the choice of payment methods among users. Therefore, payment selection is not only a matter of preference but also a reflection of broader socio-economic and infrastructural factors.

2.1.2 Performance

Organization performance can be termed as; production output, profitability, sales turnover, marketshare, and many other accounting ratios. According to Mwangi (2017), organizational performance comprises three specific areas of firm outcomes: (a) financial performance,(b) product or service market, and (c) shareholder return. Organizational performance is defined as ‘the results of operations of an organization during a given timeframe (Javed, Rafique & Tufail, 2020). Organization performance is the extent to which the organization achieves asset of pre-determined targets such as: customer value, team performance, talent management, and strategic focus all which are achieved through, proper planning, evaluation, implementation and control which can be accomplished if management has access to right knowledge and skills, proper planning, innovation and flexibility (Kamanga & Ismail, 2016). Organization performance measures consists of return on equity, profit, return on assets, market share while non-financial performance measures consist of corporate social responsibility, innovation, responsiveness and employee development (Kamanga & Ismail, 2016).

2.1.2.1 Operational Efficiency

Operational efficiency refers to the ability of organizations to deliver products or services in the most cost-effective manner while maintaining high quality. In today's competitive business environment, operational efficiency is largely driven by the integration of technology, automation, and strategic management practices. By streamlining internal processes and minimizing redundancies, firms can enhance productivity, reduce delays, and improve customer satisfaction. For instance, in the banking sector, the use of automated teller machines (ATMs), online banking platforms, and centralized data systems has allowed banks to serve more customers without increasing operational overhead (Berger & Mester, 2003). Additionally, enterprise resource planning (ERP) systems help firms coordinate operations across departments, thus avoiding duplication and improving coordination (Laudon & Laudon, 2020). In the Nigerian context, many firms have adopted digital tools to overcome infrastructure gaps and human capital constraints, thereby improving efficiency. Overall, operational efficiency contributes to a firm's ability to remain competitive and respond flexibly to market changes.

2.1.2.2 Reduced Costs

Technological advancement and process optimization have played a central role in reducing operational costs across various industries. Cost reduction involves minimizing expenditure without compromising quality or service delivery. Digital solutions such as automation, cloud computing, and data analytics eliminate the need for extensive manual labor and physical infrastructure, thereby cutting down on wages, rent, and administrative costs (Brynjolfsson & McAfee, 2014). For example, cloud-based services allow firms to store and manage data without maintaining expensive servers, while automated customer service platforms reduce the need for large call center staff. In manufacturing and logistics, the use of robotics and real-time inventory systems leads to faster production cycles and reduced wastage (Porter & Heppelmann, 2015). In Nigeria, where overhead costs like electricity and transportation can be burdensome, technology adoption has proven instrumental in reducing these burdens for businesses, especially in sectors such as fintech and telecommunications (Ojo, 2019). Therefore, reducing costs through innovation and efficiency allows firms to improve profitability and invest in expansion.

2.2 Theoretical Literature

The study examines two theories in relation to its objectives: Resource-Based View (RBV) theory and Transaction Cost Economics (TCE) theory. It is primarily based on the RBV theory, which highlights how firms can enhance their performance by effectively leveraging and integrating their internal resources, including technology and outsourcing capabilities, into their operational processes:

- i. Resource-Based View (RBV) Theory (Wernerfelt, 1984)
- ii. Transaction Cost Economics (TCE) Theory (Williamson, 1985)

2.2.1 Resource-Based View (RBV) Theory

The Resource-Based View (RBV) was first introduced by Birger Wernerfelt in his article A Resource-Based View of the Firm published in 1984. Wernerfelt argued that firms gain competitive advantage through their unique internal resources, which must be valuable, rare, inimitable, and non-substitutable (VRIN). The core

principle of RBV is that a firm's internal resources, such as technological expertise, human capital, and unique processes, can lead to superior performance if they are effectively managed and leveraged. The theory underscores the importance of resources that cannot be easily copied by competitors and which provide sustained value over time (Wernerfelt, 1984).

The relevance of RBV to the current study is significant. For pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State, the ability to integrate advanced technologies and create effective outsourcing strategies represents valuable internal resources that can directly enhance operational efficiency and reduce costs. By strategically outsourcing non-core activities, pharmaceutical firms can focus on their core competencies, such as drug production and marketing, while benefiting from the specialized skills and technologies of outsourcing partners. As noted by Barney (1991), leveraging such resources can lead to superior competitive positioning. Therefore, RBV provides a solid framework for understanding how technological advancements and outsourcing strategies can improve performance in pharmaceutical firms.

2.2.2 Transaction Cost Economics (TCE) Theory

Transaction Cost Economics (TCE) was developed by Ronald Coase (1937) and further elaborated by Oliver Williamson in the 1970s. TCE suggests that firms aim to minimize the costs associated with economic transactions. These costs include the expenses incurred from negotiating, monitoring, and enforcing contracts. According to TCE, firms decide whether to outsource or perform activities in-house based on the cost-effectiveness of each option. When transaction costs of using the market (outsourcing) are lower than those of internal production, firms are more likely to outsource (Williamson, 1985).

The relevance of TCE to the study lies in its application to the outsourcing decisions of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State. Payment selection and technological advancements can reduce transaction costs associated with outsourcing, making it a more attractive option for improving operational efficiency and cost reduction. By examining how firms balance the costs of outsourcing versus internal operations, TCE helps explain the conditions under which strategic outsourcing leads to improved performance. As Williamson (1985) emphasizes, firms must evaluate the costs of external transactions and choose outsourcing partners that minimize these costs, thus leading to better operational outcomes.

2.3 Empirical Review

2.3.1 Technological Advancements and Operational Efficiency

Nyameboame and Haddud (2017) identified key outsourced activities and to explore their influence on the organizational performance of the targeted locally owned oil and gas companies in Ghana. Also, the study explores key benefits and challenges associated with adopting outsourcing strategies. The primary data were collected using a survey from 80 participants working for different oil and gas companies in Ghana. The study revealed that most of the outsourced activities include transport services, information technology (IT) consulting and business consulting services, system infrastructure provision and management and logistical services. Also, key outsourcing reasons were reducing operational costs, avoiding major investment costs in technology, providing consistent and improved service delivery, accessing current technology and expert knowledge and focusing more on core business activities. Outsourcing is significant to enhance the performance

of an oil and gas company; however, outsourcing could also result in the conflict of firm culture with outsourced vendors, and inefficient management and loss of innovative capacity are possible negative effects of outsourcing.

Moffat (2017) examined the impact on the operational efficiency of commercial banks domiciled and operating in Kenya, which is brought about by the advancement and complexity of emerging technologies. The research hypothesis was verified via an analysis of both quantitative and qualitative data obtain over a period of five years (2012–2016). Statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS) and MS Excel were used in the detailed analysis of the data collected. To establish the associations and level of correlation between the variables under study, a multiple linear regression model was used. The study established that technological advancements in banking has positively impacted the operational efficiency of the commercial banks domiciled and operating in Kenya. The research also illustrated that mobile banking, internet banking and ATMs have a strong positive correlation with the operational efficiency of the banks as measured by the operating cost to income ratio.

Okoye-Chine (2021) examined the effect of outsourcing strategies on organizational performance of fast foods industries in South East Nigeria, as regards, cost reduction, innovation and organizational performance. The study adopted Cross-sectional design. The research instrument used in this study was structured questionnaire with 5 Likert rating scale response options. The population for this study is made up of 265 employees, selected from 10 fast food industries in South-East, Nigeria, using simple random sampling technique, convenience sampling and purposive sampling. The researcher made use of frequency distribution table, Likert scale and simple percentage in analyzing the data collected; the hypotheses for the study were tested using analysis of variance (ANOVA), correlation efficient and regression analysis in testing hypotheses, where applicable. The result from the findings revealed that outsourcing has positively and significantly affected the performance of fast food industry and the results indicated that the industry has benefited from outsourcing its business process, to reduce cost of operation. Also, the study discovered that outsourcing of certain technical aspects of business that has to do with knowledge and professionalism, enhance customers' relationship.

Obikezie and Dike (2023) investigated the effect of Human Resource Management outsourcing, BPR outsourcing and Information Communication Technology outsourcing on performance of manufacturing businesses in South-East, Nigeria. The population of the study was 1473. The statistical formula devised by Borg and Gall (1973), was employed to arrive at a sample size of 282. The population used in the analysis was 237. Pearson product moment correlation coefficient and was used in testing the hypotheses and T-test for test of significance was adopted to equally estimate for the significance of the coefficient and to ascertain whether the claim of the null or alternative hypothesis would still remain valid after the test. The result of the hypotheses shows that Human Resource Management outsourcing has a significant positive effect on competitive advantage of selected manufacturing firms in South-East, Nigeria. Business Manufacturing Process outsourcing has a significant positive effect on organizational profitability of selected manufacturing firms in South-East, Nigeria. Information Management outsourcing has a significant positive effect on cost effectiveness of selected manufacturing firms in South-East, Nigeria. Internal audit outsourcing has a significant positive effect on operational effectiveness of selected manufacturing firms in South-East, Nigeria. The study concluded that

outsourcing has a significant positive effect on competitive advantage of selected manufacturing firms in South-East, Nigeria.

El Abdi (2024) examined the factors that trigger process efficiency, which plays a mediating role in enhancing business performance in Saudi Arabia. A Pearson's correlation coefficient and several mediation analyses have been conducted in SPSS and the Process Macro by Hayes, 2022 to achieve the results statistically. The findings demonstrated a significant positive association among the critical factors in business performance, except for tech performance. While tech innovation was weak and product innovation had a moderate correlation, the other factors showcased a strong association. Further findings revealed that the product, service, market, performance, and technological innovation significantly impacted the overall business performance. At the same time, process efficiency plays a mediating role in all the models. The results emphasize that innovation is a must and process must be efficient to enhance the business performance in the long run. This research offers a reference point those businesses in a competitive environment can use to improve their operation efficiencies and effectiveness.

2.3.2 Payment Selection and Reduced Costs

Andow, Dabo and Ejeh (2018) examined the impact of outsourcing on organizational performance of listed food and beverage firms in Nigeria. The study uses a correlation design and used secondary data as the main instrument of data collected from the financial statements of the firms contained in the fact-book of the Nigeria Stock Exchange (NSE). The population and sample of the study includes all the eighteen (18) food and beverages firms listed on the floor of the Nigeria stock exchange between 2007-2016. Ordinary Least square (OLS) regression analysis using statistical package for social science (SPSS) was employed to analyze the data and test the hypotheses. The findings reveal that both business process outsourcing, and knowledge process outsourcing have a positive and significant impact on organizational performance of listed food and beverage firms in Nigeria. The study concludes that business process outsourcing, and knowledge process outsourcing have significantly impacted on the organizational performance which is profitability and competitive advantage of the listed food and beverages firms in Nigeria. The study recommends that the management of these firms should engage in outsourcing strategy in decision making by outsourcing its business processes and knowledge processes in order to increase their profit and achieve performance.

Onwuzuruike, et al., (2022) evaluated the effect of outsourcing strategies on the organizational performance of SMEs in Abuja, Nigeria: An exploratory study of fast food business in Abuja. The specific objectives were to; examine the effect of skilled staff on the profitability; the effect of cost reduction strategy on the quality of service and effect of resources reallocation strategy on the sales volume of fast food business in Abuja. A total population of three hundred and sixty-five (365), staff was used. Six (6) selected fast food businesses served as representatives of other firms in Abuja. They are: Burger Meal, Downtown Take away, Chicken Republic; Chicken Capitol Kooks Bistrol, and Obinna Fast Food Restaurant. Descriptive survey method was adopted. 227 staff returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. Data was presented and analyzed by mean score and Z – test was used to test the hypotheses.

Yang, et al., (2023) examined how different payment policies (such as recruitment and dismissal strategies and payment plans) affect the human resource market system. Based on the HRM characteristics of growth-oriented firms, we develop an agent-based model to simulate the decision-making and interaction behaviors of firms and workers. The system performance is measured by six indicators: the average profit, the profit Gini coefficient, the average output of firms, the average payment, the payment Gini coefficient, and the employment rate of workers. According to the simulation results and statistical analysis, the recruitment plan is the only key factor that significantly impacts all performance indicators other than the employment rate, and companies should pay extra attention to such plans. This study also finds that the changing worker's payment gap is influenced by industry growth and their abilities, and that the payment cap policy has a positive impact on the development of growth-oriented firms in the startup stage.

Mazikana (2023) examined the extent of outsourcing within the organisation, establishing challenges faced by Lafarge in implementing outsourcing strategies and establishing the effect of outsourcing in enhancing organisational efficiency. The researcher relied on the table developed by Krejcie and Morgan (1970) to select a sample size of 132 respondents from Lafarge. In this study respondents noted that their organisation has adopted information technology in coordinating activities with suppliers by outsourcing IT services. It was also established that outsourcing professional services are more reliable than in house services. The company outsource legal services. Some respondents noted that the organisation has been outsourcing accounting services. The study established that high levels of commitment and trust brought by outsourcing enables the organisation to attain a competitive advantage. The study established that outsourcing results in increased efficiency.

Georgewill and Obibhunun (2024) examined the influence of outsourcing strategies on organizational performance of some selected telecommunication companies in Port Harcourt Rivers State. The study adopted a survey design, the study population is 204, and sample size of 198. Purposive, simple random, systematic and stratified sampling techniques were variously employed to select the respondents. And inferential statistics were employed, and Pearson Product Moment Correlation technique was used at 0.01 level of significance with the aid of SPSS. Our findings revealed that there is a positive, strong and significant relationship between the Outsourcing strategy and measures of Organizational performance in some selected telecommunication industry Port Harcourt Rivers State. The study specifically revealed that outsourcing correlate positively and significantly with the measures of organizational performance in the area of study. The study arrives at the fact that, performance in the Nigeria telecommunication industry is premised on effective implementation of outsourcing strategy or policy.

2.4 Gap in Knowledge and Value Added

While several studies have examined the role of technological advancements in enhancing operational efficiency and the impact of payment selection on reduced costs across various sectors, such as banking, oil and gas, and fast food, there is a significant gap in understanding how these factors specifically affect the pharmaceutical industry in Enugu State. For instance, studies like those by Nyameboame and Haddud (2017), Moffat (2017), and El Abdi (2024) have shown how technological advancements and outsourcing strategies

improve operational efficiency in sectors like banking and fast food, but these findings do not address the unique technological and operational needs of pharmaceutical firms. Similarly, while Andow, Dabo, and Ejeh (2018) and Georgewill and Obibhunun (2024) explored how payment selection and outsourcing strategies positively influence performance in food and beverage and telecommunications industries, little attention has been given to how these strategies impact cost reduction within pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State. This gap in the literature highlights the need for focused research on how pharmaceutical firms in the region integrate technology and select payment strategies in outsourcing arrangements to enhance operational efficiency and reduce costs. Therefore, this study aims to address these gaps by exploring the relationships between technological advancements, payment selection, and performance in pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State.

3.0 Methodology

The study area comprised four (4) selected pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in Enugu metropolis. These firms were chosen because of their large number of staff and high ethical standards. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. A total population of 253 selected staff of the study organisations. The study made use of the whole population due to small size. Two hundred and twenty four (224) staff returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. That gave 89 percent response rate. The validity of the instrument was tested using content analysis and the result was good. The reliability was tested using the Pearson correlation coefficient (r). It gave a reliability co-efficient of 0.833 which was also good. Data was presented and analyzed by mean score and standard deviation using Sprint Likert Scale. The hypotheses were analyzed using Z – test statistic tool.

4.0 Data Presentation and Analyses

4.1.1 The relationship between technological advancements and operational efficiency of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State.

Table 4.1.1: Responses on relationship between technological advancements and operational efficiency of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State.

		5	4	3	2	1	∑FX	-	SD	Decision
		SA	A	N	DA	SD		X		
1	Advanced robotics and automation systems enhance production speed and consistency, especially in dosage formulation, packaging, and labeling.	645	180	90	24	13	952			Agree
		129	45	30	12	13	229			
		56.3	19.7	13.1	5.2	5.7	100%	4.16	1.182	
2	Automation in Manufacturing Processes Minimize human error and contamination risks in Good Manufacturing	685	180	12	20	31	928			Agree
		137	45	6	10	31	229			
		59.8	19.7	2.6	4.4	13.5	100%	4.08	1.421	

Practice (GMP)-compliant environments.

3	The use of smart sensors facilitates remote operations and monitoring, reducing the need for on-site interventions	625	180	102	20	15	942				Agree
		125	45	34	10	15	229				
		54.6	19.7	14.8	4.4	6.6	100%	4.11	1.205		
4	The automated alerts in facilities enhance workplace safety, energy efficiency, and predictive maintenance of equipment	600	308	18	4	24	954				Agree
		120	77	6	2	24	229				
		52.4	33.6	33.6	.9	10.5	100%	4.17	1.228		
5	The automated alerts in facilities enhance workplace safety, energy efficiency, and predictive maintenance of equipment	670	196	6	18	35	925				Agree
		134	49	2	9	35	298				
		58.5	21.4	.9	3.9	15.3	100%	4.04	1.461		
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								4.11	1.2994	2	

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4.1.1, 174 respondents out of 229 representing 76.0 percent agreed that advanced robotics and automation systems enhance production speed and consistency, especially in dosage formulation, packaging, and labeling with mean score 4.16 and standard deviation of 1.182. Automation in Manufacturing Processes Minimize human error and contamination risks in Good Manufacturing Practice (GMP)-compliant environments 182 respondents representing 79.5 percent agreed with mean score of 4.08 and standard deviation of 1.421. The use of smart sensors facilitates remote operations and monitoring, reducing the need for on-site interventions 197 respondents representing 74.3 percent agreed with mean score of 4.11 and standard deviation of 1.205. The automated alerts in facilities enhance workplace safety, energy efficiency, and predictive maintenance of equipment 197 respondents representing 86.0 percent agreed with mean score of 4.17 and 1.228. The automated alerts in facilities enhance workplace safety, energy efficiency, and predictive maintenance of equipment 183 respondents representing 79.9 percent agreed with a mean score of 4.04 and standard deviation 1.461

4.1.2 The relationship between payment selection and reduced costs of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State.

Table 4.1.2: Responses on relationship between payment selection and reduced costs of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State.

		5	4	3	2	1	Σ FX	-	SD	Decision
		SA	A	N	DA	SD		X		
1	Selecting the right payment methods allows pharmaceutical firms to Optimize cash flow by scheduling payments to align with revenue inflows.	415	324	6	54	36	835			Agree
		83	81	2	27	36	229			
		36.2	35.4	.9	11.8	15.7	100%	3.65	1.464	
2	Right payment methods helps to avoid unnecessary borrowing or overdraft charges due to misaligned cash disbursements.	490	356	6	4	38	894			Agree
		98	89	2	2	38	229			
		42.8	38.9	.9	.9	16.6	100%	3.90	1.402	
3	Integrating payment systems helps to Automates invoice approval, payment execution, and reporting	605	396	6	8	3	1018			Agree
		121	99	2	4	3	229			
		52.8	43.2	.9	1.7	1.3	100%	4.45	.727	
4	Payment systems helps reduce manual errors and time delays, leading to streamlined operations and lower administrative overhead	530	456	6	12	1	1005			Agree
		106	114	2	6	1	229			
		46.3	49.8	.9	2.6	.4	100%	4.39	.683	
5	Secure and verifiable payment methods Lower the risk of fraud and financial losses, especially in high-value pharmaceutical transactions	440	416	6	44	13	919			Agree
		88	104	2	22	13	229			
		38.4	45.4	.9	9.6	5.7	100%	4.01	1.137	
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								4.08	1.0826	

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4.1.2, 164 respondents out of 229 representing 71.6 percent agreed that selecting the right payment methods allows pharmaceutical firms to Optimize cash flow by scheduling payments to align with revenue inflows with mean score 3.65 and standard deviation of 1.464. Right payment methods helps to avoid unnecessary borrowing or overdraft charges due to misaligned cash disbursements 187 respondents representing 81.7 percent agreed with mean score of 3.90 and standard deviation of 1.402. Integrating payment systems helps to Automates invoice approval, payment execution, and reporting 220 respondents representing 96.0 percent agreed with mean score of 4.45 and standard deviation of .727. Payment systems helps reduce manual errors and time delays, leading to streamlined operations and lower administrative overhead 220 respondents representing 96.1 percent agreed with mean score of 4.39 and .683. Secure and verifiable payment methods lower the risk of fraud and financial losses, especially in high-value pharmaceutical transactions 192 respondents representing 83.8 percent agreed with a mean score of 4.01 and standard deviation 1.137

4.2 Test of Hypotheses

4.2.1 Hypotheses One: Technological advancements have no positive relationship with operational efficiency of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State.

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

	Advanced robotics and automation systems enhance production speed and consistency, especially in dosage formulation, packaging, and labeling.	Automation in Manufacturing Processes Minimize human error and contamination risks in Good Manufacturing Practice (GMP)-compliant environments.	The use of smart sensors facilitates remote operations and monitoring, reducing the need for on-site interventions.	The automated alerts in facilities enhance workplace safety, energy efficiency, and predictive maintenance of equipment.	By integrating modern technologies into core functions, pharmaceutical companies meet regulatory standards and respond swiftly to market demands.
N	229	229	229	229	229
Uniform Parameters ^a	Minimum 1	1	1	1	1
^b	Maximum 5	5	5	5	5
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute Positive .563	.598	.546	.610	.585
	Negative -.563	-.598	-.546	-.610	-.585

Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z	8.525	9.053	8.260	9.235	8.855
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

a. Test distribution is Uniform.

b. Calculated from data.

Decision Rule

If the calculated Z-value is greater than the critical Z-value (i.e $Z_{cal} > Z_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis accordingly.

Result

With Kolmogorov-Smirnon Z – value ranges from $8.525 < 9.235$ and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000, the responses from the respondents as display in the table is normally distributed. This affirms the assertion of the most of the respondents that **Technological advancements had significant positive relationship with operational efficiency of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State.**

Decision

Furthermore, comparing the calculated Z- value ranges from $8.525 < 9.235$ against the critical Z- value of 0.000 (2-tailed test at 95 percent level of confidence) the null hypothesis were rejected. Thus the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that **Technological advancements had significant positive relationship with operational efficiency of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State.**

4.2.2 Hypotheses Two: Payment selection has no positive relationship with reduced costs of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State.

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

	Selecting the right payment methods allows pharmaceutical firms to Optimize cash flow by scheduling payments to align with revenue inflows.	Right payment methods helps to avoid unnecessary borrowing or overdraft charges due to misaligned cash disbursements	Integrating payment systems helps to Automates invoice approval, payment execution, and reporting.	Payment systems helps reduce manual errors and time delays, leading to streamlined operations and lower administrative overhead	Secure and verifiable payment methods Lower the risk of fraud and financial losses, especially in high-value pharmaceutical transactions.
N	229	229	229	229	229
Uniform Minimum	1	1	1	1	1

Parameters ^a		5	5	5	5	5
^b Maximum						
Most Absolute		.466	.567	.711	.711	.588
Extreme Positive		.157	.166	.013	.004	.057
Differences Negative		-.466	-.567	-.711	-.711	-.588
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		7.054	8.574	10.755	10.755	8.905
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

a. Test distribution is Uniform.

b. Calculated from data.

Decision Rule

If the calculated Z-value is greater than the critical Z-value (i.e $Z_{cal} > Z_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis accordingly.

Result

With Kolmogorov-Smirnon Z – value ranges from $7.054 < 10.755$ and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000, the responses from the respondents as display in the table is normally distributed. This affirms the assertion of the most of the respondents that **Payment selection had significant positive relationship with reduced costs of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State.**

Decision

Furthermore, comparing the calculated Z- value ranges from $7.054 < 10.755$ against the critical Z- value of 0.000 (2-tailed test at 95 percent level of confidence) the null hypothesis were rejected. Thus the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that **Payment selection had significant positive relationship with reduced costs of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State.**

4.3 Discuss of Findings

From the result of hypotheses one, the calculated Z- value ranges from $8.525 < 9.235$ against the critical Z- value of 0.000 which implies that **Technological advancements had significant positive relationship with operational efficiency of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State. In the support of the result in the literature,**

From the result of hypotheses two, the calculated Z- value ranges from $7.054 < 10.755$ against the critical Z- value of 0.000 which implies that **Payment selection had significant positive relationship with reduced costs of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State. In the support of the result in the literature,**

5.0 Summary of Findings, Conclusion and Recommendations

5.1 Summary of Findings,

i. Technological advancements had significant positive relationship with operational efficiency of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State, $Z(9.235, P. <.05)$

ii. Payment selection had significant positive relationship with reduced costs of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State $Z(10.755, P. <.05)$

5.2 Conclusion

The study concluded that Technological advancements and Payment selection had significant positive relationship with operational efficiency and reduced costs of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State. Strategic outsourcing in the pharmaceutical industry involves contracting out non-core business functions such as research and development (R&D), manufacturing, logistics, and IT services to external specialists. This allows pharmaceutical firms to focus on their core competencies, such as drug discovery and market expansion. Outsourcing is a strategic tool used to reduce operational costs, improve efficiency, accelerate time-to-market, and access specialized expertise or technology, Firms may outsource clinical trials to Contract Research Organizations (CROs) or manufacturing to Contract Manufacturing Organizations (CMOs). In summary, strategic outsourcing enhances the performance of pharmaceutical firms when aligned with organizational goals, backed by clear contracts, and managed through effective risk mitigation strategies.

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the findings, the study recommended that:

- i. Pharmaceutical firms should adopt advanced manufacturing systems such as Continuous Manufacturing (CM) and Process Analytical Technology (PAT). These technologies allow for, Real-time monitoring and control of production processes, and reduced downtime and waste, and faster product throughput and improved quality assurance.
- ii. The Pharmaceutical firms should adopt Electronic Payment Systems (e-Payments) to Reduces administrative costs associated with paper checks and manual processing, enhance payment speed and accuracy, reducing late payment penalties and improves traceability and transparency for audits and reporting.

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